

NUMERICAL DECISIONS OF THE PROBLEM OF THE CENTRIFUGAL SEPARATOR BASED ON THE SARC TURBULENCE MODEL

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Abstract

The results of mathematical modeling of a two-phase swirling turbulent flow in the separation zone of a centrifugal apparatus are presented. The motion of the carrier gas flow was modeled using the averaged Navier - Stokes equations, for the closure of which the well-known turbulence model by Schur and Spalart was used, the amendment to the Spalart-Allmaras SARC model. Based on the obtained field of averaged velocities of the carrier medium, taking into account turbulent diffusion. The article compared the results taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air and without taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air.

Keywords: Spalarta Allmares, centrifugal air separator, Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes equations, stream function, vorticity, iteration, rotation correction, eddy viscosity, sweep, upper relaxation.

Introduction

Multiphase turbulent swirl flows are widely used to intensify heat and mass transfer processes in various industrial apparatuses. Examples of such apparatuses are chemical reactors, combustion chambers, dust collectors, separators, etc. In this work, we study a two-phase turbulent flow in a centrifugal separator and present a comparative one taking into account the influence of the solid phase on the air and without taking into account the influence of the solid phase on the air based on the turbulent model with rotation correction (SARC) [1]. Physical and mathematical formulations of the problem: It is known that swirling flows are characterized by a strong curvature of streamlines, the appearance of recirculation zones, the location and dimensions of which largely depend on the twist intensity and the configuration of the boundaries. In addition, such flows are turbulent. Therefore, their study requires the involvement of effective turbulence models. Recently, quite effective turbulence models have appeared. These methods were further modified for turbulent flows with a small swirl [1]. However, verification of these models for strongly swirling flows showed that their accuracy is insufficient, and these models for rotating flows do not

have an advantage over others. Therefore, in the present work, for the numerical study of the flow in the separator, we use a well-tested modification model (Spalart Allmares), M.L. Shura (SARC).

In this paper, we consider a three-dimensional turbulent flow in an air-centrifugal separator, which is an important link in the processes of separation and classification of particles, obtaining powders of the required quality. The efficiency of the processes involved in the separation of powders into coarse and fine fractions will depend on how the structure of the flow is organized inside the workspace. The aim of the undertaken numerical study is to clarify the nature of the hydrodynamics of the swirling flow at different geometries. The scheme of the calculated area is shown in (Fig. 1). Centrifugal air separator operates as follows. The source material, together with the primary air, is fed through a pipe to the upper part of the separator. Using controlled shovels, a rotational movement is imparted to the air flow. Under the action of centrifugal inertia, the particles move to the cylindrical wall of the separator body and fall into the classification zone located between the cones and the walls (see Fig. 1). Large particles due to their greater mass under the

action of centrifugal force accumulate near the inner wall of the separator housing and by inertia fall into the separator hopper. And small particles are carried away by air and carried out of the separator through the outlet pipe. Thus, the starting material is divided into two fractions. It is easy to understand that the effectiveness of such a separator is highly dependent on its geometry. Therefore, to find the optimal geometric parameters, the problem arises of modeling the kinematics of particles inside the installation. It is clear that the kinematics of particles depends on the dynamics of the air flow. Therefore, two tasks arise here: 1) study of the dynamics of the air flow; 2) based on the obtained hydrodynamic parameters of the air flow, the study of the trajectories of the separated particles.

In practice, the bulk density of dust in separators can reach 50 g / m³. This value is significantly lower than the density of incompressible air (2.5 kg / m³). Therefore, in many works, the influence of the solid phase on the dynamics of air is neglected. However, near the wall where dust particles accumulate under the action of centrifugal force, the density of the solid phase can reach significant values. In this case, the influence of the solid phase on the dynamics of the gas phase cannot be neglected. Therefore, in this work, a numerical study of the turbulent flow is carried out taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow and without taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow inside the centrifugal installation. The modeling of three-dimensional gas flows is associated with well-known practical difficulties: the use of spaced grids, the slow convergence of a numerical solution algorithm, and a rather complicated implementation of the calculation algorithm. Solving the turbulent problem also requires thickening the calculated stack in areas with large gradients of the desired variables, as well as near solid walls. All these problems significantly complicate the physical and mathematical formulation of the problem in the field under consideration.

For a numerical study of the problem, a system of equations is used; the Reynolds averaged Navier-Stokes equations in a cylindrical coordinate system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial U}{\partial z} + V \frac{\partial U}{\partial r} + \frac{W}{r} \frac{\partial U}{\partial \varphi} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r(v+v_t) \frac{\partial U}{\partial r} \right) - \frac{\rho_p}{\rho} k(U - U_p) \\ \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial V}{\partial z} + V \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} + \frac{W}{r} \frac{\partial V}{\partial \varphi} - \frac{W^2}{r} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r(v+v_t) \frac{\partial V}{\partial r} \right) - \frac{\mu}{r^2} V - \frac{\rho_p}{\rho} k(V - V_p) \\ \frac{\partial W}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial W}{\partial z} + V \frac{\partial W}{\partial r} + \frac{W}{r} \frac{\partial W}{\partial \varphi} - \frac{WV}{r} + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial \varphi} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r(v+v_t) \frac{\partial W}{\partial r} \right) - \frac{(v+v_t)W}{r^2} - \frac{\rho_p}{\rho} k(W - W_p) \\ \frac{\partial U_p}{\partial t} + U_p \frac{\partial U_p}{\partial z} + V_p \frac{\partial U_p}{\partial r} = k(U - U_p) \\ \frac{\partial V_p}{\partial t} + U_p \frac{\partial V_p}{\partial z} + V_p \frac{\partial V_p}{\partial r} = k(V - V_p) \\ \frac{\partial \rho_p}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(U_p \rho_p)}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial(V_p \rho_p)}{\partial r} = D \left(\frac{\partial^2 \rho_p}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \rho_p}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 \rho_p}{\partial z^2} \right) \\ D = -\frac{\rho}{\rho + \rho_p} \frac{v+v_t}{S_c} \end{cases}$$

In this system, U, V, W– are respectively the axial, radial, and tangential components of the airflow velocity vector; U_p, V_p - similar components of the velocity vector for the i-th dust fraction; P– pressure; ρ– gas density; ν is its molecular viscosity; ν_t is the turbulent viscosity of the air flow; ρ₀ mass density of dust of different sizes; k is the coefficient of interaction between air and the i-th dust fraction; D is the diffusion coefficient of the solid phase, Sc = 0.8– Schmidt coefficient. The initial and boundary conditions for the system of equations (1) are set in a standard way [3].

The interaction coefficient between the phases is determined as the Stokes parameter:

$$k = \frac{18\rho\nu}{\rho_p\delta^2}.$$

In this expression, ρ₀ is the density of the material of the dust particles, δ is the “effective” particle diameter.

System (1) is open. To close the Reynolds equations, we used the turbulent models SA and SARC. Spalart-Allmaras model [6] – This model belongs to the class of one-parameter turbulence models. Only one additional equation appears here for calculating the kinematic coefficient of vortex viscosity

$$\frac{\partial \rho \tilde{\nu}}{\partial t} + \dots = \dots \tilde{\nu} \quad (2)$$

Turbulent eddy viscosity is calculated from:

$$\nu_t = \tilde{\nu} f_{\nu 1}$$

The SARC model is the same as for the “standard” version (SA), except that the term Pv is multiplied by the rotation function fr1 cm in [1,4]. The remaining values remain the same as for the “standard” model, which are presented in [1].

For the numerical implementation of system (1), partial parabolization was performed, i.e. in the right-hand sides, the terms with derivatives with respect to z are neglected. A stream function ψ is introduced for which the continuity condition is satisfied

$$V = -\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z}, \quad U = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} \quad (4)$$

The vorticity ζ is also introduced

$$\zeta = \frac{\partial U}{\partial r} - \frac{\partial V}{\partial z} \quad (5)$$

Next, we exclude pressure from the first two equations of system (1) and substituting expressions (4) into (5) we obtain a system with respect to new variables.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial z} + V \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial r} - \xi \frac{V}{r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial G^2}{\partial z} = -\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r(v_{eff}) \frac{\partial U}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} \left(r(v_{eff}) \frac{\partial U}{\partial r} \right) - \\ - \frac{k}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} (\rho_r (U - U_r)) - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_r (V - V_r)) \right), \\ \frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial G}{\partial z} + V \frac{\partial G}{\partial r} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r v_{eff} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial G}{\partial r} - \frac{G}{r^2} \right) \right) - \frac{\mu}{r^2} G, \\ \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial r^2} - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial z^2} = \zeta, \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial z} + V \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial r} = (P_v - D_v) + \frac{1}{\sigma_v} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left[r(v_{eff}) \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial r} \right] + \frac{C_{b2}}{\sigma_v} \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial r} \right)^2, \\ G = W \times r, \quad v_{eff} = v + v_r. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Here v_{eff} -effective viscosity.

The main section was disassembled into 4 sections shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. The main section of the separator.

Where R is the large radius of the annular channel, therefore, the surface of the cone corresponds to; r_1 is the radius of the inner cylinder of the first sections, r_3 , r_4 is the radius of the inner cylinder of the rub and fourth section.

For the numerical implementation of system (6), a coordinate transformation was carried out

The first section is $0 < z < z_2$.

$$\eta = \frac{\eta_0 F_1(z) - F_2(z)}{F_1(z) - F_2(z)} + \frac{(1 - \eta_0)r}{F_1(z) - F_2(z)};$$

$$F_1(z) = R, \quad F_2(z) = r_2$$

The second section is $z_2 < z < z_3$.

$$\eta = \frac{r - F_2(z)}{(F_1(z) - F_2(z))};$$

$$F_1(z) = R, \quad F_2(z) = 0.$$

The third section is $z_3 < z < z_4, \eta < \eta_0$.

$$\eta = \eta_0 \frac{r}{F_3(z)};$$

$$F_3(z) = r_2, \quad F_2(z) = 0.$$

The fourth section is $z_3 < z < z_4, \eta > \eta_0$.

$$\eta = \frac{\eta_0 F_1(z) - F_2(z)}{F_1(z) - F_2(z)} + \frac{(1 - \eta_0)r}{F_1(z) - F_2(z)};$$

$$F_1(z) = R, \quad F_2(z) = r_4.$$

Here, $F_1(z)$ is the function of the outer cylinder, $F_2(z)$, $F_3(z)$ is the function of the inner cylinder and cone, $\eta_0 = 0.6\eta$.

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial z} + U \eta \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \eta} + V \eta \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \eta} - \xi \frac{V}{r} + \frac{1}{r^2 L} \frac{\partial G^2}{\partial z} + \frac{\eta}{r^2} \frac{\partial G^2}{\partial \eta} = -\frac{\eta}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r(v_{eff}) \xi) + \frac{\eta^2}{r} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \eta^2} (r(v_{eff}) \xi) - \\ - \frac{k}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial r} (\rho_r (U - U_r)) - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (\rho_r (V - V_r)) - \eta \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} (\rho_r (V - V_r)) \right); \\ \frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial G}{\partial z} + U \eta \frac{\partial G}{\partial \eta} + V \eta \frac{\partial G}{\partial \eta} = \eta \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \left(v_{eff} \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial \eta} - \frac{G}{r} \right) \right) - \frac{\mu}{r^2} G; \\ \frac{\eta^2}{r} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \eta^2} - \frac{\eta}{r^2} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \eta} + \frac{1}{r L^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial z^2} + \frac{2\eta}{r L} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial z \partial \eta} + (\eta)^2 \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \eta^2} + \eta \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \eta} = \zeta; \\ \frac{\partial U_r}{\partial t} + U_r \frac{\partial U_r}{\partial z} + U_r \eta \frac{\partial U_r}{\partial \eta} + V_r \eta \frac{\partial U_r}{\partial \eta} = k(U - U_r); \\ \frac{\partial V_r}{\partial t} + U_r \frac{\partial V_r}{\partial z} + U_r \eta \frac{\partial V_r}{\partial \eta} + V_r \eta \frac{\partial V_r}{\partial \eta} = k(V - V_r); \\ \frac{\partial \rho_r}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial (U_r \rho_r)}{\partial z} + \eta \frac{\partial (U_r \rho_r)}{\partial \eta} + \eta \frac{\partial (V_r \rho_r)}{\partial \eta} = D \left(\eta^2 \frac{\partial^2 \rho_r}{\partial \eta^2} + r \frac{\partial \rho_r}{\partial \eta} + \frac{\partial^2 \rho_r}{\partial z^2} + 2\eta \frac{\partial^2 \rho_r}{\partial z \partial \eta} + (\eta)^2 \frac{\partial^2 \rho_r}{\partial \eta^2} + \eta \frac{\partial \rho_r}{\partial \eta} \right); \\ \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial z} + U \eta \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial \eta} + V \eta \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial \eta} = (P_v - D_v) + \frac{\eta}{r \sigma_v} \frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \left[r(v_{eff}) \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial \eta} \right] + \frac{C_{b2}}{\sigma_v} \left(\eta \frac{\partial \tilde{v}}{\partial \eta} \right)^2. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Thus, the new variables make it possible to bring all the equations of the system to a parabolic form and this system can be written in vector form

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x} + V \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} = v \frac{\partial^2 \Phi}{\partial y^2} \quad (8)$$

In this equation:

$$\Phi = \begin{bmatrix} \zeta \\ G \\ \tilde{v} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\frac{\Phi_{i,j}^{n+1} - \Phi_{i,j}^n}{\Delta t} + 0.5 \cdot (U + |U|) \frac{\Phi_{i,j}^n - \Phi_{i-1,j}^n}{\Delta \zeta} + 0.5 \cdot (U - |U|) \frac{\Phi_{i,j+1}^n - \Phi_{i,j}^n}{\Delta \zeta} +$$

$$+ 0.5 \cdot (V + |V|) \frac{\Phi_{i,j}^n - \Phi_{i,j-1}^n}{\Delta \eta} + 0.5 \cdot (V - |V|) \frac{\Phi_{i,j+1}^n - \Phi_{i,j}^n}{\Delta \eta} = v \frac{\Phi_{i,j+1}^n - 2\Phi_{i,j}^n + \Phi_{i,j-1}^n}{\Delta \eta^2}$$

For the numerical implementation of ζ , G , and v from equation (8), an implicit scheme was used.

For the numerical implementation of ψ from equation (8), the iteration method was used, and this equation is equal to this

$$\frac{\psi^{k,i+1,j} - 2\psi^{k+1,i,j} + \psi^{k,i-1,j} + \psi^{k,i,j+1} - \psi^{k,i,j-1}}{\Delta \zeta^2} +$$

$$+ \frac{\psi^{k,i+1,j+1} - \psi^{k,i-1,j+1} + \psi^{k,i+1,j-1} - \psi^{k,i-1,j-1} + \psi^{k,i,j+1} - 2\psi^{k+1,i,j} + \psi^{k,i,j-1}}{2\Delta \zeta \Delta \eta} = r_j \xi_{i,j}^k$$

This scheme is absolutely stable and the unknowns on a new layer were found by sweep method. The integration steps were $\Delta \xi = 0.05$, $\Delta \eta = 0.02$. The number of design points in the transverse direction was 50, the longitudinal direction was 100. For the problem, the following boundary conditions were set: on the wall, i.e. all speeds will be zero, and on the

wasps for $\Phi = U, W, v$ and $V = 0$. To start the calculation, we set the values $\nu = 3 / Re$ for the Reynolds number $Re = 10000$.

To ensure stability in the numerical solution of system (7), a difference scheme against the flow was used, and the diffusion terms were approximated by the central difference. The Poisson equation for the stream function was also approximated by the central difference, and the iteration method of upper relaxation was used to resolve it. The initial and boundary conditions for equation (2,3,6) are set in the standard way [1,2,3].

The discussion of the results

Figure 3-illustrates air velocity profiles in the section $\zeta = 0.65$. Here $U / U_{ref}, V / V_{ref}, W / W_{ref}$ are dimensionless velocities; at the initial, the tangential velocity is $W / U_{ref} = 0.5$.

Figure 4-illustrates the air velocity profiles in the section $\zeta = 0.65$. Here, $U / U_{ref}, V / V_{ref}$, and W / W_{ref} are dimensionless velocities; at the initial, the tangential velocity is $W / U_{ref} = 1$.

c)

Fig.3. Profiles a) axial, b) radial, and c) tangential air velocity in the section $\zeta = 0.65$. 1-taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow, 2-without taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow.

a)

b)

a)

b)

c)

Fig. 4. Profiles a) axial, b) radial, and c) tangential air velocity in the section $\zeta = 0.65$. 1-taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow, 2-without taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow

Figure 5-illustrates air velocity profiles in the section $\zeta = 0.65$. Here U / U_{ref} , V / V_{ref} , W / W_{ref} are dimensionless velocities; at the initial, the tangential velocity is $W / U_{ref} = 1.5$.

a)

b)

c)

Fig.5. Profiles a) axial, b) radial, and c) tangential air velocity in the section $\zeta = 0.65$. 1-taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow, 2-without taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow

Figure 6-illustrates air velocity profiles in the section $\zeta = 0.65$. Here U / U_{ref} , V / V_{ref} , W / W_{ref} are dimensionless velocities; at the initial tangential velocity is $W / U_{ref} = 2$.

a)

b)

Fig.6. Profiles a) axial, b) radial, and c) tangential air velocity in the section $\zeta = 0.65$. 1-taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow, 2-without taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow

Conclusions

A mathematical model is developed for calculating the hydrodynamics of a swirling turbulent flow arising in an air-centrifugal separator. The basic laws of such a flow are revealed and it is shown that geometric parameters have a significant effect on aerodynamics in the separation zone of a centrifugal apparatus. The presented mathematical model allows not only to study the complex picture of the swirling turbulent flow, which contributes to the development of new promising methods for the classification of powders, but also to optimize the operating and geometric parameters of existing plants. The results were compared taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow and without taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow.

It can be seen from the presented figures that the numerical results of the SARC model, taking into account the effect of the solid phase on the air flow and without taking into account the influence of the solid phase on the air flow, differ quite significantly with an increase in centrifugal speed. This means that with an increase in centrifugal velocity closer to the walls, the turbulent layer expands accordingly, this zone of dust particles moves randomly, this affects the flow velocity.

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